

Cytomorphological Study of Thyroid Lesions According to Bethesda System and Its Correlation with Radiological and Thyroid Function Tests

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Abstract:

Background: FNAC is a useful diagnostic tool which is inexpensive, easy to use, safe, minimally invasive & easily available time saving OPD procedure. The 6 tier Bethesda system offers consistent terminology for thyroid reports and permits improved discussion and comprehension between the clinician and the pathologists. It has been found that FNAC along with thyroid hormone profile helps us at arriving to an accurate diagnosis. FNAC also helps to minimize the incidence of thyroidectomy and to choose treatment for the patient. To differentiate benign and malignant thyroid swelling ultrasound is safe and cost effective investigation of choice. The American College of Radiology has recommended the ACR- TIRADS reporting system for thyroid swellings on ultrasound. Thyroid function test findings can be used to predict the physiological status of thyroid lesions, and imaging cytological correlation can assist minimize inaccurate findings from fine needle aspiration of thyroid nodules.

Materials & Methods: For this hospital-based prospective study at Silchar Medical College and Hospital, 120 fine-needle aspirated tests of thyroid nodules were collected over a period of one year. The classification of all diagnoses resulting from fine needle aspiration cytology took into account factors such as age, gender, cytological results (TBSRTC), and radiological abnormalities (TIRADS). These will be correlated with the findings of thyroid function testing.

Results: The 120 thyroid lesions that were assessed were distributed as follows: 3.17% were classified as Non-Diagnostic (ND), 1.17% as Suspicious for Malignancy (SFM), 4.17% as Follicular Neoplasm (FN), 85.83% as Benign, and 0.83% as Atypia of Undetermined Significance (AUS). Most individuals classified as category II had abnormal Thyroid Function Tests (TFT). In category VI, all 5 cases were euthyroid, with no cases showing altered TFT. Among the 15 cases of thyroiditis, most were hypothyroid. Out of 120 cases, highest distributions of cases were in TIRADS 2 followed by TIRADS 3(USG).

Conclusion: The combined use of FNAC with the Bethesda system, TI-RADS, and TFTs helps pathologists and clinicians by providing a comprehensive evaluation of thyroid nodules. This approach allows for accurate differentiation between cancerous and benign growths which aids in assessing the need for further investigation. It not only standardizes the diagnostic criteria but also offers clinicians clear management guidelines, whether that be follow-up FNAC or proceeding to surgery. By integrating cytological, radiological, and functional assessments, unnecessary surgeries can be avoided, as only nodules with a high risk of malignancy or significant abnormalities are selected for surgical intervention, ensuring more precise and effective patient care.

Keywords: Fnac, Bethesda, thyroid lesion, Tirads and thyroid function test.

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Introduction

Thyroid lesions are frequently encountered in clinical practice and can range from benign nodules to malignant tumors. Determining the proper clinical care and prognosis requires an accurate diagnosis. Because it is easy to use, safe, and a good way to tell benign when it comes to detecting thyroid nodules that are aggressive, FNAC has taken the lead. A consistent classification approach for analyzing the results of FNA cytology is offered

by the Bethesda approach for Reporting Thyroid Cytopathology (TBSRTC), aiding in consistent communication among clinicians and improving patient management strategies (Cibas & Ali, 2009). [1]The TBSRTC is a thyroid cytopathology reporting system that consists of six categories: non-diagnostic, benign, atypia of undetermined significance (AUS), suspicious for follicular

neoplasm (SFN), suspicious for malignancy (SM), and malignant. [2]

FNA is frequently combined with radiological imaging, particularly ultrasound, to assess the thyroid lesions & its structural characteristics. For risk assessment and characteristics of such thyroid nodules its size, composition, echogenicity, and the existence of calcifications or vascular patterns are crucial. (Gharib et al., 2010). [3]

TIRADS is an ultrasound-based categorization technique that was initially created to enhance the thyroid nodule identification process during FNAC, hence averting unnecessary surgeries. [4]

Furthermore, thyroid function tests (TFTs) are essential for determining the thyroid gland's operational condition and can offer oblique hints regarding the type of thyroid lesion. TFTs check the levels of free thyroxine (FT4), free triiodothyronine (FT3), and thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) in the serum.

The relationship between cytomorphological findings, radiographic features, and thyroid function test results has been investigated in a number of research in an effort to improve thyroid lesion therapy and diagnostic precision. One study conducted by Baloch et al. (2011) [5] demonstrated that integrating cytological assessment with ultrasonographic findings and TFTs improves the preoperative diagnostic accuracy for thyroid malignancies. This comprehensive approach allows for better identification of high-risk lesions, reduces unnecessary surgeries, and provides a more tailored treatment plan for patients.

This study's goal is to investigate the Bethesda system's cytomorphological patterns of thyroid nodules and connect the results with thyroid function tests and radiological imaging. By doing so, we hope to provide a more comprehensive diagnostic framework that enhances the accuracy of thyroid nodule evaluation and optimizes patient outcomes.

Materials & Methods

This study was a hospital-based prospective study, including a final sample size of 120 patients. Conducted over a period of one year from September 2023 to August 2024 of individuals presenting with thyroid nodules at Silchar Medical College and Hospital. Eligible participants included patients with thyroid nodules, regardless of age, gender, or religious background, who had undergone Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC), Ultrasonography (USG), and thyroid function tests. Patients with thyroid lesions who had not completed these diagnostic evaluations were excluded from the study.

Data for this study were collected from cytology records from the Pathology Department, USG reports from the Radiology Department, and thyroid function test results from the Biochemistry Department. The study procedure began with a comprehensive clinical evaluation, which included a detailed medical history, a general physical examination, and an assessment focused specifically on the thyroid gland. The findings from the thyroid function tests and USG reports were documented along with it.

Prior to performing the FNAC procedure, patients received an explanation of the technique and provided informed consent. FNAC was then carried out using a disposable 10-cc syringe fitted with a 23-gauge needle. Smears were prepared from the aspirated samples and were immediately fixed with methanol after air-drying, followed by staining with May Grunwald Giemsa. Reporting was based on the morphological criteria outlined in the Bethesda System for Reporting Thyroid Cytopathology (TBSRTC), and cytological features were carefully assessed according to these guidelines.

Results

The age range of the 120 thyroid FNAC cases that were analyzed was 11 to 80 years, with the age group of 31 to 40 years accounting for the largest proportion of cases (39 instances, or 32.5%) among the cases. 42.20 years old was the mean age. There were 19 male patients (15.8%) and 101 patients (84.2%) who were female. The ratio of male to female was 1:5.

Among the 120 cases studied, the majority fell into category II (85.8%), while category III had the fewest cases (0.8%). Within category II, the predominant findings were benign thyroid lesions, such as colloid nodules or adenomatoid nodules, which comprised 86 of the 120 cases.

Following this were cases of granulomatous thyroiditis (2 out of 120) and lymphocytic/Hashimoto's thyroiditis (15 out of 120). Cases that were classified as category I (3.3%) contained only aspirated cyst fluid and no cellularity or colloid.

A diagnosis of follicular neoplasm (TBSRTC IV) was made after five of the 120 patients showed highly cellular smears with homogeneous follicular cells organized in packed clusters and micro follicles.

There were 5 cases (4.1%) of malignant lesions in category VI: 3 cases of papillary thyroid cancer were discovered, 1 case was found to be anaplastic thyroid carcinoma, and 1 case was found to be medullary thyroid cancer. The outcomes we were able to obtain are listed in Table No. 1 below.

Table 1: Case Distribution in the Current Study Based on TBSRTC

TBSRTC Category	Cases	Percentage
Category I (Non diagnostic)	04	3.33%
Category II (Benign)	103	85.83%
Category III (Atypia of Undetermined significance)	01	0.83%
Category IV (follicular neoplasm)	05	4.17%
Category V (suspicious for malignancy)	02	1.67%
Category VI (malignant)	05	4.17%
Total	120	100%

Figure 1: (a) Category I (Non diagnostic) - FNAC yields few cyst macrophage & blood only (MGG,10x) ; (b) & (c) Category II (Benign) - thyroid follicles in a colloid background (MGG,40x) & Granulomatous thyroiditis - epithelioid cells with giant cells(MGG,40x); (d) Category III (Atypia of Undetermined significance) - Some follicular cells with hyperchromasia and nuclear enlargement (MGG,40x); (e) Category IV (Follicular neoplasm) - small uniform nuclei of follicular cells arranged in microfollicles (MGG,40x); (f) & (g) Category V (Suspicious for malignancy) - follicular cells showing nuclear enlargement, macronucleoli, anisonucleosis (marked with arrow)- Suspicious for Papillary carcinoma (MGG,40x); (h) & (i) Category VI (Malignant)- Papillary carcinoma showing intranuclear cytoplasmic pseudoinclusion & nuclear grooving(marked with arrow) (MGG,40x).

Based on ultrasound imaging, most thyroid nodules are categorized as TIRADS 2 or TIRADS 3. Out of the 120 nodules, 36 were classified under TIRADS 3, 10 under TIRADS 4, and 4 under TIRADS 5. Of these, 43 were classified under TIRADS 2. Nodules

categorized as it was believed that Bethesda I and II seemed benign, but Bethesda IV–VI were considered cancerous.

The outcomes we were able to gather are listed in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Correlation of Bethesda Categories with TIRADS

Bethesda	Tirads 1	Tirads 2	Tirads 3	Tirads 4	Tirads 5	Total
I	03	01	0	0	0	04
II	24	42	30	07	0	103
III	0	0	01	00	0	01
IV	0	0	04	01	0	05
V	0	0	0	02	0	02
VI	0	0	01	0	04	05
Total	27	43	36	10	04	120

No one of the forty-three TIRADS 2 nodules was found to be malignant, as none of them fell into the Bethesda IV or above category. 30 of the 36 nodules with the TIRADS 3 classification were in Bethesda II, four in Bethesda IV, and one in each of Bethesda III and VI.

A small number of nodules that looked suspicious enough on ultrasound to be placed under TIRADS 4 were found to be benign when classed under Bethesda. Ten instances of suspicious nodules, two cases of papillary thyroid cancer (classified as BSRTC V based on cytomorphological features), seven cases of benign Bethesda II, and one case under Bethesda IV were included in TIRADS 4. Only malignant instances were included in TIRADS 5 (4 cases) and BSRTC V (5 cases).

Colloid or adenomatoid nodules among the benign lesions had a varied distribution across TIRADS and Bethesda categories. However, the malignant lesions that were recorded as such were papillary thyroid cancer and medullary thyroid carcinoma.

The highest number of instances in category II with modified TFT were discovered. Comparatively, category VI did not contain a single instance of a modified TFT (Table 2). Out of the 17 instances of thyroiditis in category II, the majority (15 cases of lymphocytic/Hashimoto's thyroiditis and 2 cases of granulomatous thyroiditis) were hypothyroid. The majority of the 96 cases with benign thyroid lesions (55 out of 96) were euthyroid. The correlation between Bethesda category and thyroid function test are tabulated below in Table 3.

Table 3: Correlation of Bethesda Categories with thyroid function tests:

Thyroid Function Test	TBSTRC						TOTAL
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	
Hyperthyroid	0	16	0	0	0	0	16
Euthyroid	03	55	01	04	01	05	69
Hypothyroid	01	32	0	01	01	0	35
Total	04	103	01	05	02	05	120

Discussion:

For assessing thyroid lesions, most people agree that FNAC is the primary diagnostic technique. Its effectiveness is significantly enhanced when combined with clinical factors such as patient age, sex, ultrasound imaging, and thyroid function tests, which together increase the procedure's diagnostic precision. The Bethesda System's standardized terminology facilitates better communication between pathologists and surgeons, helping them make more informed decisions regarding patient management and minimizing unnecessary surgeries. This system's clear categorization into six groups simplifies classification compared to previous reporting methods.

The study's mean age of 42.20 years is in good agreement with studies by Mostafa EA et al [6] and Biswas A et al [7], which found that at presentation, the mean ages were 42.98 and 41.54 years, respectively. There were 120 patients in the research. There were 19 males (15.8%) and 101 females (84%) in the study, which is in line with

the findings of Mostafa EA et al [6] and Periakaruppan G [4], who found that there were, respectively, 84.7% females and 15.2% males and 84.8% females and 15.2% males. Study done by Acharya K et al [9] (2022) included 134 thyroid lesions in which the female population outnumbered the male population by a male to female ratio of 1:5.3; which has similar finding with our study of 120 cases where male to female ratio is 1:5.

In this study the distribution of patients examines the groups based on TBSRTC with results from other investigations. Consistently across all investigations, the majority of cases were classified as benign.

The Bethesda system advises restricting the use of category III (AUS) due to its variability, as it is somewhat heterogeneous and subject to interpretation. While the majority of cases may be correctly diagnosed by FNAC, there are difficulties with unclear categories like AUS and those that seem suggestive for follicular neoplasm. Under

these circumstances, molecular testing for somatic mutations, as those identified in RAS, RET/PTC, PAX8/PPAR γ , BRAF, and RAS, can enhance the cytological evaluation and facilitate better management choices. Every case underwent thyroid function testing (TFTs), which were classified based on TBSRTC. The findings were then compared with studies by Mehrotra et al. and Khatib Y et al. [7] Among the TFTs, TSH levels are the most sensitive indicator, while total T3 and total T4 levels can be affected by non-thyroid illnesses. In this study, cases were classified as euthyroid, hypothyroid, or hyperthyroid based on TSH levels. TFTs were altered in 49 cases with benign lesions, of which 16 were hyperthyroid and 33 were hypothyroid, while the remaining 58 cases were euthyroid, which aligns with findings by Khatib Y et al. [8] All cases in categories III and VI were euthyroid, and most cases in categories IV and V were euthyroid as well, except for one hypothyroid case in each category. The study done by Yadav R et al (2023) [10] shows most cases were euthyroid (76%), predominantly classified as Category 2. A strong correlation between cytological diagnoses and thyroid hormone levels ($p=0.04$) was observed.

Certain characteristics, like nuclear grooves, chromatin clearance, and overlapping nuclei, can occasionally make diagnosis difficult. Verifying TFT levels, which are frequently increased, in these circumstances can be especially beneficial in elucidating the diagnosis.

A common challenge in diagnosing papillary carcinoma is when it coexists with a cyst. However, difficulties can also arise when papillary carcinoma is present alongside a nodular colloid goiter without cystic changes, as the carcinoma may be hidden by the goiter, which constitutes the majority of the swelling. In many circumstances, especially in patients with chronic goiters, a strong index of suspicion and a careful assessment of nuclear characteristics are necessary. Because the thyroid scan and antibody panel analysis were not available at the hospital, neither of the subjects in this study had one of these procedures. A substantial percentage of good FNAC smear results were obtained in spite of these restrictions.

According to reports employing the TBSRTC, FNAC efficiently distinguishes between cancerous and benign thyroid nodules, excluding follicular neoplasms, where it is necessary to show capsular and/or vascular invasion, which is not something that can be determined by cytology alone. This differentiation guides the management plan, while biochemical tests assist in determining whether a combined medical and surgical approach is necessary for each patient. Most cases of thyroiditis were found to be hypothyroid (10 out of 15), followed by euthyroid (4 out of 15), with only one

case being hyperthyroid, which corresponds with Khatib Y et al.'s findings. [8]

Conclusion

When it comes to bridge the gap between surgeon & pathologist, the Bethesda System for Reporting Thyroid Cytology is the gold standard. Thyroid FNA smears can be easily reported using a straightforward, standardized process that offers management guidelines: the Bethesda categories. Diagnostic issues arise when aspirate samples are insufficient, either in terms of quality or quantity, to conclusively rule out neoplastic activity. Correlations between clinical, TFT, and USG are very helpful in these circumstances. Thyroid function test alterations are linked to benign disorders, primarily thyroiditis with hypothyroidism, and can help identify benign lesions with unusual characteristics.

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